

Diffusion of calcium chloride in single germinating chickpea seed at 298.16 and 318.16 K

M. L. Sood* and Ashima Passi

Department of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141 004, India

E-mail : mlsoodmaxicom.online.com Fax : 91-0161-400945

Manuscript received 12 March 2001, revised 30 August 2001, accepted 10 September 2001

The theory of diffusion of electrolytes and non-electrolytes has been applied for the determination of diffusion coefficients of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in a single seed of a promising chickpea variety, PBG-1 at 25 and 45° and in the concentration range 0.01–1.0 M. The results indicate that the diffusion coefficients first decreased and then increased with electrolytic concentration. Role of hydration number also formed a part of the study.

We have earlier developed a theory of diffusion and carried out extensive studies of diffusion of simple valence salts in wheat seeds and pollen grains¹. In the present communication we have extended our study to germinating chickpea, PBG-1 seeds, and diffusion coefficients of calcium chloride determined at two temperatures, viz. 298.16 and 318.16 K.

Fig. 1. Plots of \bar{D} and D vs \sqrt{C} for CaCl_2 -PBG-1 (chickpea) system at 25°.

Results and Discussion

The integral (\bar{D}) and differential (D) diffusion coefficients were determined by the procedure discussed elsewhere²⁻⁴. The plots of \bar{D} and D vs \sqrt{C} at 25 and 45° in the concentration range 0.1–0.1 M are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. From the results it is clear that the diffusion coefficients of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in chickpea variety, PBG-1 followed a general trend at both the temperatures. The diffusion rate was found to decrease and then increase with electrolytic concentration. A similar behavior was also observed in the case of NaCl diffusion in wheat variety⁴, HD 2329. Hydration number⁵ of Ca^{II} ion is 12 and the theoretically⁶ calculated primary and secondary hydration numbers for the ion are 3 and 7.40 (total hydration number is 10.40). From the results

Fig. 2. Plots of \bar{D} and D vs \sqrt{C} for CaCl_2 -PBG-1 (chickpea) system at 45°.

at two different temperatures it can be inferred that Ca^{II} ion alongwith its primary hydration shell and loosely held secondary hydration shell, contribute equally towards D values at certain concentrations, while at other concentrations the effects of primary and secondary hydration have significant role and cannot be ignored.

Experimental

Seeds of a promising chickpea variety, PBG-1 were procured from the Department of Plant Breeding, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana. Calcium chloride ($\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and KCl (AnalaR) were used.

In our earlier²⁻⁴ studies, wheat and corn seeds in bulk were employed in diffusion experiments and the volume of the diffusion cell taken was 23 ml. In the present work the diffusion cell volume was reduced to 10 ml without making any other alterations in the design of the original diffusion cell² and single seed was employed for all diffusion experiments. With this reduction in volume, the change in solution concentration with time during diffusion process becomes measurable. Except for the above change in volume

of the diffusion cell, the methodology employed for determining seed constant and diffusion coefficients from experimental data was the same as reported earlier²⁻⁴. The seed constant (β_{seed}) obtained for PBG-1 chickpea variety at 25^o was 0.0928. Since seed constant is assumed to be constant² with temperature, the above value was also employed for the determination of diffusion coefficients at 318.16 K.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M.L.S.) is thankful to his wife Nishi and to Mrs. Poonam Verma for encouragement.

References

1. M. L. Sood, *Seed Sci. Technol.*, 1987, **15**, 255.
2. M. L. Sood and J. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **65**, 17.
3. M. L. Sood and R. Dhir, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 425.
4. M. L. Sood and R. Dhir, *Seed Res.*, 2000, **28**, 22.
5. R. H. Stokes and R. A. Robinson, "Electrolyte Solutions", 3rd. ed., Butterworths, London, 1959.
6. M. L. Sood, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 17.